

GENERAL INFORMATION ABOUT CONSTRUCTIVE ELEMENTS OF THE BUILDING

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Abstract: Buildings consist of various structural elements. Each building element has its own function. The article provides general information about each structural element in the building and their functions.

Key word: Construction, building, structure, construction, wall, masonry, concrete Building constructions, their names and functions are listed below:

1. Foundations are the underground part of the building, which bear the weight of the building

are constructions that accept it and transfer it to the base.

2. Walls are an internal and external barrier according to their function and location, that is, an element that protects a room from the influence of the external environment or separates rooms from each other.

Walls are divided into load-bearing and non-load-bearing types.

Structures, equipment located above load-bearing walls,

supports the weight of furniture and the like. Also

Both internal and external walls can be load-bearing. Buildings

barrier (curtain) dividing into small rooms, non-load-bearing walls

is considered Such walls are usually without foundations. Barrier function retaining walls themselves, resting on the foundations or the foundation beam to be in the form of hanging walls that are supported and hung on columns possible

3. Separate supports - falling from the roof covering and intermediate coverings are load-bearing elements in a vertical position that transmit the load to the foundation (columns, pillars).

4. Inter-floor coverings - divides the internal space of the building into floors and the so-called "progon khari" rigel, which is specially attached to the columns laid on the beams, and in some cases directly on the column is fixed. Inter-floor coverings for permanent and temporary loads together with the lifting connects the walls, their priority provides and increases the spatial uniformity of the entire building.

Intermediate closures are as follows depending on their location in the building:

- inter-floor closures (divides the building into floors);
- basement partition (separates the first floor from the basement);
- attic covering (separates the top floor from the attic).

5. Roof - atmospheric precipitation of the building structure and rooms and construction that protects against other types of negative effects. It is upstairs

consists of covering, covering with attic and without attic, and roof covering will be Attic is the roof covering of the upper floor of the building the space between consists of part.

In a roof without an attic, the roof is combined with the covering of the upper floor of the building

will be Roofs can be sloped and flat. A break from flat roofs can be used as a receiving area and for other purposes.

6. Stairs - connect the floors of the building and take people out of the building also serves as an evacuation. It consists of stair marches and stair landings.

The architectural-compositional solution of the balcony, loggia and bay windows of the building

are important structural elements that enrich. They surround additional elements connecting the interior of the room with standing nature performs its function. They are especially important in residential buildings.

7. Elevators — used in five or more residential buildings. They are

There are three types:

- ❖ For the service of people;
- ❖ For loads (in industrial buildings);
- ❖ Service (medical) elevators.

The main element of elevators consists of a cabin suspended by steel ropes on a lifting "winch" installed in the machine compartment.

will be The elevator shaft is wrapped on four sides along its entire height

and in its lower part, a cavity with a height of 1300 mm and shock absorbers and towing equipment are placed there. Car section should be located in the upper or lower part of the mine possible

At present, the walls of elevator shafts installed in residential buildings are mostly made of prefabricated reinforced concrete elements with a thickness of 120 mm. It is advisable to install the elevator shafts in front of the stairs. The structures listed above are the main structures of the building. In addition to the main load-bearing structures, the building has secondary structural elements without which the building cannot perform its functions.

or to the building they are auxiliary structural elements (balconies, loggia, etc.). bay windows) will be designed as. They consist of:

1. Balconies — a load-bearing reinforced concrete slab, floor and wrapper consisting of elements, it is hung on the wall with one side and to the anchors left in the wall and to the inter-floor covering panels is welded.
2. Loggias - one side facing the front of the building is open, and three sides from a structural element surrounded by a load-bearing wall consists of Loggias are installed only to protect the room from the sun, they are found only in buildings built in the southern regions.
3. Bay windows, protruding from the front part of the room, building a known one with one or more windows, surrounded by an external wall

is said to the piece. Installation of bay windows is multi-level, starting from the first floor

more important for buildings. In this case, the one that surrounds the bay window a separate foundation is built on the walls. The level of illumination of the bay windows in the room

and because of increased sunlight, they are more in the northern regions and it is built in places with a moderate climate.

4. Doors - connect the rooms to each other, to the room

way in and out. They are on the wall or curtain

it consists of a door frame, a door box (piece) and a plate on the wall.

Apart from these, other structural elements in residential buildings, i.e

It can be a porch, porch, canopy over the door, etc.

5. Windows - light, sunlight and

serves for rooms. They are clothes instead of clothes

It consists of layers of clothing and clothing.

6. Floors - on various bases, for example, often on lagas, reinforced concrete

over the cladding panel or, in a building without a "basement", below the first floor directly impermeable base is cut.

The floor is considered to be the highest level or the real floor. The floor material is provided to the surface level in advance. In this case, the underlying leveling layer can be made of concrete, cement-sand mixture, asphalt or plaster.

The floor is the base of the interfloor partition, and the partition is the riser is a construction. In this case, there will be no concrete layer to be placed under it. Soundproof, heat and waterproof to the floor structure layers can be added. The function of the building and work According to the nature of the release processes, the floors should be ripe, and the heat is low the conductor should be non-slip, non-swelling when wet, beautiful in appearance, dust-proof, noiseless, easy to clean, industrial and cheap. Floors in rooms with high humidity should be moisture-resistant and waterproof, and in fire-hazardous buildings, they should be non-combustible. Depending on the construction of the floor, it can be integral, cast, made of separate elements and made of flexible soft roll materials. Depending on the materials, the floors are divided into types such as wooden boards, parquet, linoleum, ceramic tiles, and cement. Composite floors include cement floors, mosaic floors, asphalt floors, mastic floors, and earthen floors.

Summary. In conclusion, we need to know this information in order to control the construction of structural elements of buildings based on their norms. Otherwise, there is no question that the building will become uninhabitable or unfit for use.

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